

Actin tail detection in fluorescence microscopic image sequences to investigate the cause of movement of subviral particles

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Abstract: The subviral particles of the Marburg virus occasionally show an actin tail along their travelled path. This actin tail is detected by an algorithm to facilitate further examined of actin-based movement. Using fluorescence image sequences and the coordinates of the particle tracks, the average brightnesses can be measured within 9 examination areas around the subviral particle. The measured actin brightness is set into relation to the temporal subviral particle's velocity. The results show that it is possible to find temporal correlations between actin intensity and particle speed using the presented method. However, still the method is sensitive to interfering factors.

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I. Introduction

In order to cure or control a disease, it is necessary to understand how it manages to harm the body. With this knowledge, a medicine, a therapy or similar can then be developed. This understanding is often difficult to obtain and requires a number of trials. The current pandemic situation shows how important the time factor and the necessary automation are in such an approach. It must be checked as quickly as possible whether, for example, a medicine shows the desired efficacy.

For locomotion in the cell, many viruses use microtubule-based mechanisms. Experiments with Marburg virus have shown that locomotion is primarily actin-based. At this stage, this is a unique example of subviral particles in mammalian cells, over long distances. During locomotion, a so-called actin tail is seen in some cases. [1, 2].

This project approaches the detection of the actin tail of subviral particles of the Marburg virus in fluorescence microscopic image sequences, which together with the Ebolavirus forms the family of filoviruses. The influence of actin on the locomotion of the subviral particles in cells will be investigated. Previous work has shown that the brightness of the labeled actin trails changes in a sequence. Thereby, it was observed that in moments of subviral particle acceleration, the actin sometimes appears brighter [2]. In this work, an automated algorithm is developed to measure the brightness differences around the subviral particle over time to detect the actin tail.

II. Material and methods

For the studies, fluorescence image sequences were kindly provided by the Institute of Virology at the Philipps-University of Marburg, Germany, derived from an innovative method for fluorescence live cell imaging [3]. In addition, an automated tracking algorithm, introduced by Kienzle et

Figure 1: Section of an image from the fluorescence image sequences. The subviral particles are shown in green. The actin in a cell is shown in red. (2) The particle chosen as an example for this paper. (3) The actin tail to be detected.

al. [4] and further developed by Rausch et al. [5], was applied to automatically track subviral particles.

The image sequences are divided into two channels: actin (red) and subviral particle (green). The red channel images that contain information about the intracellular actin distribution are the basis for the following methods. The position data of all particles are read from the data using the tracking algorithm and are stored. The background array is generated by calculating the average value of each pixel of the entire image sequence. It is subtracted from each image to generate a homogenous background for each frame. Additionally, cubic spline interpolation is applied to the newly generated image.

The coordinates are extracted for the track to be examined. Subsequently, each image is examined individually. The

orientation of each detected subviral particle is calculated from the tracking data. Therefore, the angle is calculated between the X-axis and the vector from a previous and a future coordinate. This information is used to deduce where the rear end of the particle is located. Nine measuring areas are placed around the subviral particle with respect to its orientation as illustrated in Fig. 2. The center's location is given by the coordinates of the particle. The individual areas are fanned out in a circular pattern. Examination area 4 is positioned at a fixed distance behind the particle with the angular information. Afterwards, examination area 1 is defined by a rotation matrix with the angle 45° . For the further examination areas this proceeds analogously. The mean pixel brightness of each window is determined. The 9 values are stored in an array. When all images have been examined, a diagram can be created from the array. Likewise, the mean value and standard deviation over all 9 examination areas in each individual image can be calculated from it.

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the 9 examination areas. Examination area 5 is located exactly above the subviral particle. Examination area 4 is located behind the particle. Note the red actin tail.

In addition, the velocity of the particles in each individual frame is calculated. For this purpose, the vector between the coordinate [i] and the coordinate [i+1] is computed. The length of the vector indicates the distance between the two points in pixels. This is calculated with the pixel size and the temporal distance between the images, so that one gets the velocity in nm/s.

III. Results and discussion

As an example, a single track is analyzed. The graphs mentioned in "Material and Methods" that can be generated from the array show the image number of the fluorescence image sequences on the X-axis and the actin brightness on the Y-axis. Idealized, the following results should be expected: Examination area 4 is located behind the particle and since an actin tail should be detectable there, an increased brightness value is expected. Examination areas 1 and 7 may also show increased values, e.g. in the case of a curve, whereas the remaining examination areas should show low values. As examination area 4 extracts the most significant information, this publication focuses on its measurements. However, due to the fact that the particles move distributed over the entire cell, the paths frequently

cross. Another factor why there are increases in the brightness value in all examination areas is that the actin is rather active in some frames than in others. Although the subtraction of the mean value of each pixel with the examined pixel minimizes this effect it cannot be entirely suppressed.

In Fig. 4, the examination area 4 is shown in relation to the velocity of the particle. On the X-axis the image number of the fluorescence image sequences is depicted. On the left Y-axis the brightness value is plotted. On the right Y-axis the velocity in nm/s can be read. Image 25 - 65 shows a good relationship between brightness and velocity. In the following, this is no longer so clearly visible. A high velocity is reached from image 175, i.e. approx. 30 images after the plotted deflection of the brightness at examination area 4. This dependence is not observed for other tracks.

Figure 3: Relationship between velocity [nm/s] and actin brightness behind the particle over the image sequence from the example particle.

IV. Conclusions

An actin tail could be detected for individual tracks. This indicates the operability of the presented method. However, the isolation of a track and its surround in images should be improved in future work. This turned out to be difficult, as tracks often randomly cross with other tracks. This leads to errors, so an actin tail can be detected, but it originates from a different particle. Important task is to reliably reproduce the correct position of the particle.

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